

Colonial History on Animals' Bodies: A Study on the Shikar Writings of Lt. William Rice

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Abstract

Shikar literature is a vibrant but now ignored genre of literature among academic circles. Shikar literature deals with writings related to the act of hunting wild animals and exploration of jungles. The British administration in the nineteenth and early twentieth century India was interested not just in establishing its authority and control over the populace of India and its territories, it also aimed subtly to colonise the Indian jungles and the wild animals. Hunting and colonial policies on wildlife enabled the Colonisers to reshape their interactions with the natives of India and their compatriots- the wild animals. Hunting in the Indian wild was deeply implicated in the colonial state's exercise of power after the first Indian War of Independence in 1857. Therefore, British policies on wildlife in the nineteenth catergorised wild animals as "vermins" and encouraged the white hunters to eradicate those vermins. An attempt has been made in this paper to review the shikar writings of William Rice, one the earliest Shikar writers in Colonised India.

Keywords

Hunting, Shikar Literature, Colonialism in India.

Introduction

When the East India Company first arrived in India, they made it their mission to control the Indian subcontinent. Apart from establishing political control over India, they also sought to bring the region's vast forests under control. Colonial hunting in India emerged as a part of the rise of the British colonial state and established itself as a new imperial ideology of dominance[1]. India's dark and dangerous forests that sheltered creatures of most hideous and dangerous manifestations posed a threat to the British Authority[2]. Hence, hunting became an opportunity for the British to show off masculinity and establish a total control over the territory they rule over with pride. Thus, shikaris or hunting trips used to be undertaken regularly[3]. Some of these hunters, took themselves into recording these shikaris in their writings as well. These hunter-writers roamed freely in continents and countries that boasted of dense forests full of flora and fauna, hunting wild animals and birds. Some hunted only for some specific purposes such as eliminating threat to crops or to hunt animals like tigers and leopards that have turned into man eaters. But a large group of hunters hunted for pleasure, to get skin, ivory, leather and other animal derivatives to be kept or sold as trophies. An enquiry into the writings of such *shikaris* will reveal how a particular society or culture responds to nature and environment. By one estimate, between 1875 and 1925 alone, some 80,000 tigers were killed in India. Bounty and sports hunting were rampant - kings and officials killed tigers in their thousands, using guns, spears, nets, traps and poison[4]. Thus, the early colonial period in India witnessed an uncontrolled, wanton killing of wild animals.

Objective of study

1. To identify the imperial voice in the shikar writings of William Rice
2. To examine the writings of early colonial hunters from an ecocritical perspective
3. To examine how the early colonial hunters in India paved way for a rapid deterioration of Indian wild Life.

Review of Literature

Colonel Julius Barras, in his memoir *India and Tiger Hunting* (1883) records his experiences of hunting tigers in India. His work restricts itself to the processes associated with hunting tigers. Colonel Barras does not seem to be a poetic admirer of nature or a person with a conservation bent of mind. However, his work remains to be one of the finest early shikar writings. He mentions that one of the most curious features of tiger shooting is the "extraordinary tenacity with which both the Europeans and natives engaged in the sport adhere to certain traditions" (P.17). Apart from revealing how this pastime habit of the colonial officers in India became an engaging activity for both the coloniser and the native, this also sheds light on how the act of hunting became a mass hysteria along the forest lands leading to ajeopardy of Indian wild.

Sporting Days in Southern India by A.J.O Pollock (1894) in another early shikar writing from the Indian subcontinent

Like other colonial masters, Pollock too thinks of the big game hunting as an activity of pleasure seeking. On one occasion, he admits to having shot a panthress along with three unborn cubs in the stomach. "A post-mortem revealed three unborn cubs about the size of rats, which although devoid of hair, bare the marks of all the rosettes very clearly"(p.54). While the native Indians regarded the felines in the Indian Jungle with respect and fear and gave them a wider berth, the colonialist in India saw tigers, leopards and panthers as animals to be conquered and destroyed. Pollock's narrative reveals the brutal necessities of the colonial hunters in India.

Main Text

Tiger-shooting in India by William Rice- The Colonial hunter versus the Colonised Animals:

William Rice was a Lieutenant in the 25th Regiment Bombay Native Infantry[5] and later he became Captain in the Turkish Regiment. He had written two books on his hunting experiences in India: *Indian Game: from quail to tiger* (1884) and *Tiger-shooting in India. Being an account of hunting experiences on foot in Rajpootana, during the hot seasons, from 1850 to 1854* (1857).

William Rice, in his book *Tiger Shooting in India* (1857) claims that during his one year's sport in *Rajpootana* (Rajasthan), his "bag" consisted of 156 head of "large game" killed and wounded, as follows - 68 tigers killed, 30 wounded, total 98, Panthers killed 3, wounded 4, total 7, Bears killed 251 wounded 26, total 51." Whether exaggerated or not, this statistic specifically explains two phenomenon - the reasons for the decline of wildlife in India. Two, wounded carnivores becoming man-eaters. Moreover, many British officers employed in India had also taken recourse into Indian jungles for generating revenue. Dane Hucklebridge points out: "when Britain took India as a colonial possession, it did far more than simply "introduce a new power structure or administrative policy-it affectively turned the entirety of its foreign possessions into an engine of revenue, which meant exploitation of natural resources on a massive, multifaced scale" (p. 117).

The account of William Rice also reveals that many colonial Shikaris like him did not just resort to wanton killings, some of those acts were very irresponsible too. A wounded animal is not followed up and left by a colonial hunter - either to die a painful death or to get its wounds and to become a man-eater. In some cases, the mother was killed leaving the cubs back. In the absence of proper training and care of their mother, the cubs would either die of starvation or become preys to other predators. In extreme cases they may become crude hunters - hunting livestock or human beings in hamlets bordering forestlands. An account of William Rice:

I saw an old bear lying asleep at the mouth of a large cave, at least two hundred yards of, across a deep ravine. Fired Three shots at her as she bolted down the hill, on being woke up by my first bullet. Afterwards, we went round and saw plenty of blood, but did not attempt to follow up this bear, she bolted, growling, and was accompanied by half-grown cub, that also came out the cave.

The colonial hunter considered the wild animals of Indian jungles as his enemies, just he had considered the natives as his enemies. Reminiscenting the adventure of following up a wild tiger, William Rice writes, "Almost directly the beating commenced, our enemy appeared most unexpectedly close. We instantly greeted her with the contents of our double rifles.... This was a fine tigress, with a fine bright skin." The skin of a killed animal appears to be lucrative means which has made many colonial officers tiger hunters.

William Rice, in the Preface, writes that his objective is to give to the best of his abilities, "some account of the most exciting and glorious sport this world affords-tiger shooting". Here, by "this world", William Rice invariably meant India, where tigers-the Royal Bengal Tigers – were in large numbers. Though his objective was to shoot tigers, he actually shot almost all animals in the jungle upon getting an opportunity. Moreover, he had left 30 wounded tigers, 4 wounded leopards and 26 wounded bears behind in a year's shooting "adventure". He states that "provided we certain that there was little chance in getting a shot at any wild beast in the neighbourhood, we seldom neglected killing Sambur, solely for the sake of their skins" (p.53). He also seems to be quite oblivious regarding how man-eaters are created:

Here, an old man told of a tiger that had killed several of his cattle. Without some such provocation, we found the people of this country very unwilling to inform against the tigers, or even to admit that such animals existed at all in their neighbourhood. This, no doubt, partly arises from a superstitious idea they have that, it merely wounded, the tiger or his relations will revenge himself either on them or their cattle.

What William Rice labels as superstition is actually an experience of the jungle talk that the wounded tigers, if not always, often become man eaters.

With this ignorance, coupled with an unrestrained concern for his own safety, William Rice, had left many tigers wounded and not, following them up "we now tried for the other two wounded tigers, but could only take up their prints and blood for a short distance, owing to the dense jungle and rocky nature of the ground. These beasts, by us, were following each other out of this cover, going very slowly, and rolling and staggering along. It was now getting late, so we left of hunting for them any longer". (p163).

However, the colonial hunter is compassionate about those animals that are tamed and submissive. During one of the hunting expeditions of William Rice, a panther had attacked and killed the pet dog of Mr. Lord, the shooting accomplice of William Rice. This happened at night, and unlike chasing the animals they wounded, they did not hesitate to go deep into the Jungle to retrieve the dog's body. And, words of compassion describe the loss: "Poor Tim was quite dead, having received a blow of the panther's paw. Next morning, we erected a cairn to his memory, for he was a great pet....." (p.208). The compassion for pet dog is understandable. However, the wanton killing of the wild animals, allowing many wounded animals to go away suffer in agony puts William Rice and such other colonial hunters in a precariously paradoxical position.

Conclusion

The relationship between animal studies, ecocriticism and postcolonial studies is marked by tension as well by continuity (Miller: 6). A study of shikar literature will enable us to unpack the political literary and ecological histories behind such colonialist narratives. Imperial hunting was a forceful marker of social status, calling a feudal system of land access, power, patronage and privilege (John Miller. P11). The colonial hunter did not distinguish the natives of India from the wild animals in Indian forests[6]. Therefore, colonizing the native had to have a parallel in the form of colonizing the animal/ wild. Just like the colonial histories are written on the native state/ body of the native, the colonial ruler did the same on the body of bet animals as well.

An ecocritical reading of such writings reveals that most of the species concerned in shikar literature are carnivores and large home range species which are important from a conservation point of view. The early colonial hunters like William Rice lacked vision and compassion regarding wildlife and conservation. Therefore, such writings do not bear any sense of remorse or regret and they were able to collect "trophies" by hunting tigers, and leopards and elephants in the jungles of India.

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Endnote

1. 2. It is a lesser-known fact that "411 species of mammals, 1232 birds, 456 reptiles, 219 amphibians, 2546 fish and 83,436 kinds of invertebrates and over 50,000 plant species" have been identified to be in the Indian Subcontinent. India has set up" 104 National Parks, 18 bio reserves and more than 515 sanctuaries to protect and preserve these species; It is also said that "12.6%. avian, 7.6%. mammals, 6.2% reptiles and 6.0% species of flowers" are native to India. It is also true that around "33% plant species are endemic to India and hence it is one of

the biodiversity reserves in the world with around 70% endemic and diverse plants and animal species". (Vijay Gonekar. P242).

3. The tradition of 'shikar' or organised big game hunting in India dates back to the 18th century, when army officers and civil servants employed by the Honourable East India Company (HEIC) began to hunt tigers, bears, antelope, elephants and a variety of other exotic species during their leisure time, usually as the guests of Indian maharajas and princes. Over the years, the term shikar began to embrace a number other sporting activities introduced to India by the British Raj or ruling class, including gamebird shooting, angling, pig sticking and fox or jackal hunting carried out by foxhounds imported from England. Accessed on 5.02.2026.

4. Accessed on 5.02.2026.

5. Known as 25th Regiment of Bombay Native (Light) Infantry in the Bombay Army. Established in 1820, it was also known as 125th Napier's Rifles in the Indian Army under the then East India Company.

6. The British satirical magazine Punch had published the political cartoon of a fierce lion pouncing on a snarling Bengal tiger on the 22nd of August 1857. Captioned, the British lion's vengeance on the Bengal tiger, this cartoon had come about after London had been alerted to the possible recruitment of some 30,000 men for curbing the rebellion in British India.